

A STUDY OF THE ART OF PRINTING AND THE STATUS OF HOUSE IN THE HOROSCOPIES OF PRINTING PRESS WORKERS

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Abstract:

In this article, the relationship between Printing and Astrology has been explored using traditional astrology methods. This thesis is made with 3rd House, 11th House, 10th House, Mercury and Saturn.

Key Words: 3rd House, 11th House, Mercury, Saturn, Lagna & 10th House.

Introduction:

If one wants to be excellent in the field of printing, his horoscope should have Gemini, its lord Mercury, third house and third house lord, Aquarius, its lord Saturn, 11th house and 11th house lord are all strong. Why here we taking Gemini as its lord Mercury and Aquarius as its lord Saturn? According to the Kalapurusha philosophy, the third house is the bava which refers to all works related to writing. According to kalapurusha tattva this Bava is called Mithunam. Its lord is Mercury, and education's karaka butan here. The work of the third bava's are education, writing related, deed recording related, computer related, education related, accounting related, all these are related to numbers and words. We take this 3rd Bava and its lord Mercury for this study because there are more karakas related to numbers and words than other planets.

A Scientific View of Mercury:

Mercury is the closest planet to the Sun. It is also the smallest planet in the solar system. It takes 88 days to go around the sun once. Seen from Earth it appears to take 116 days. No natural moons are known for it. The planet is named after the Roman messenger god 'Mercury' in Western culture. 'Budhan' is the cause of knowledge in Indian culture; Named after God. Because Mercury's angular separation from the Sun is low (at most only 28.3°), Mercury is rare to see, mostly due to the brightness of the Sun. Our ancestors say, even if our witnesses get kshabon they don't get Mercury'. Morning or evening twilight is the perfect time to see Mercury. Because Mercury lacks an atmosphere to retain heat from the Sun, Mercury's surface experiences greater temperature fluctuations than any other planet. Near the equator it is 700 m (427 °F; 800 °C) during the day and 100 m (-173 °F; -280 °C) at night. It is always coldest at the terminals (poles) below 180 M (-93 °F; -136 °C). Mercury's axis has the lowest inclination (about 1/30 degree) in the Solar System. But its orbital deviation is very high. Mercury is almost similar in appearance to Earth's moon. It is characterized by many large pits (craters) with a cut space. Like Earth, Mercury has no atmosphere. But unlike Earth, it doesn't have seasons like most other planets. Mercury has a metal as large as iron. Due to this, Mercury also has some magnetic field. When we look at the statement in this science, it is known that there are iron ores in the planet Mercury. Saturn is the ruler of iron. So we know that there is a similarity in nature between Mercury and Saturn.

A Scientific View of Saturn:

Saturn is the sixth planet from the Sun and the second-largest in the Solar System, after Jupiter. It is a gas giant with an average radius of about nine-and-a-half times that of Earth. It has only one-eighth the average density of Earth, but is over 95 times more massive. Even though Saturn is nearly the size of Jupiter, Saturn has less than one-third of Jupiter's mass. Saturn orbits the Sun at a distance of 9.59 AU (1,434 million km) with an orbital period of 29.45 years. Saturn's interior is thought to be composed of a rocky core, surrounded by a deep layer of metallic hydrogen, an intermediate layer of liquid hydrogen and liquid helium, and finally, a gaseous outer layer. Saturn has a pale yellow hue due to ammonia crystals in its upper atmosphere. An electrical current within the metallic hydrogen layer is thought to give rise to Saturn's planetary magnetic field, which is weaker than Earth's, but which has a magnetic moment 580 times that of Earth due to Saturn's larger size. Saturn's magnetic field strength is around one-twentieth of Jupiter's. The outer atmosphere is generally bland and lacking in contrast, although long-lived features can appear. Wind speeds on Saturn can reach 1,800 kilometres per hour (1,100 miles per hour).

The planet has a bright and extensive ring system composed mainly of ice particles, with a smaller amount of rocky debris and dust. At least 146 moons are known to orbit the planet, of which 63 are officially named; this does not include the hundreds of moonlets in its rings. Titan, Saturn's largest moon and the second largest in the Solar System, is larger (while less massive) than the planet Mercury and is the only moon in the Solar System to have a substantial atmosphere. Saturn is named after the Roman god of wealth and agriculture and father of Jupiter. Its astronomical symbol (♄) has been traced back to the Greek Oxyrhynchus Papyri, where it can be seen to be a Greek kappa-rho ligature with a horizontal stroke, as an abbreviation for *Κρόνος* (Cronus), the Greek name for the planet. It later came to look like a lower-case Greek eta, with the cross added at the top in the 16th century to Christianize this pagan symbol. The Romans named the seventh day of the week Saturday, *Sāturni diēs* ("Saturn's Day"), for the planet Saturn.

Let's See the Characters of 12 Houses:

1st House Characters:

Denoting the head, denoting the brain in the head, denoting one's unique talent, leaders, possessing leadership qualities, talented, honorable, self-knowledgeable, yoga to experience anything, success or failure, immunity in the body, sense of self,

money. Emphasis on prestige, thought processes, self-efforts efficiency, health, generosity, administrative ability, discipline, ability to achieve in a field.

2nd House Characters:

Second house refers to the facial organs like eyes, nose, mouth, tongue, teeth, jaw, chin, throat etc. Ability to speak to explain one's own opinion, structure of consuming delicious food, structure of face, vision, cash flow, wealth, easily convertible objects, yoga for enjoying one's wealth, easily convertible objects like grains, metals, gems, jewelry, gold, silver and add family members, All education comes under second house.

3rd House Characters:

Ear, shoulder, hands, neck, nervous system in the body below the neck, blood vessels, sense organs, Third house means writing, so all kinds of communication, exchange of information, contracts, shoulder hands, Vijaya, Viriyam, Courage, Confidence, Fortitude, Determination, Perseverance, Little Trips, Little Success, Post Offices, Telephone, Radio, News, Shrinking Anything, Badges, Certificates, Cheques, All Records in the World, Messengers, Journalism, advertising, library, printing, printing industry, leasing, rumours, confusion, brain washing comes under third house.

4th House Characters:

4th house, Estate, vehicle, mother, one's comfort, one's immovable property, movable property, lungs, heart, all similar productive activities, education, land, grain fields, farms, buildings, memorials, antiques, fixed objects, producing the same kind of m/c, primary school, treasures, mines, household goods, surplus money, ancestral property, well, river, lake, grave comes under 4th house.

5th House Characters:

Love, physical attractiveness, commentary, beauty, intelligent thinking, physical morals, memorization, raw materials, origin, intelligence, power to create a life, entertainment, beautification, frolic, taste, interest in art, Lack of physical work, deep thinking, excessive indulgence in sensuality, business like commission, calculation of the number of one's children, sports etc.

6th House Characters:

This is the Bhava of the Stomach; it is a Bhava that refers to the bile inside the stomach, the liver and diseases related to these. Work for wages, understanding of work in others, labourers, enmity, litigation, avarice, greed, arrogance, boasting, usurpation of another's property, doing better than others, temporary credit or debt, solitude, prison, lonely life, neglect by others.

7th House Characters:

Married life, life partner details, people with a lot of public relations, no one likes to look good in front of the crowd, public support, public meeting, details of theft, hostile touch, pleasant exchanges, long-term habits with others, Business, partners in business, alliances, open character of Jataka, tendency to involve others in anything, second child, respect for other people's opinions, dependence on others are the Karakas of Seventh house.

8th House Characters:

In the anatomy, the eighth house represents the mysterious organs, the eighth house determines the extent of the Jataka's life, i.e. life span and the environment in which death takes place. Negative events such as pain, agony, betrayal, grief, misfortune, struggle, accident, repair of body parts, theft of the horoscope's property by others, illegal actions of the horoscope, cross paths, etc., which bring harm to the ascendant, are the karakas of the eighth house. Also suicide, murder, mutilation of body parts, robbery, harassment by enemies, all kinds of obstacles, waste, loss, insurance, life inheritance, charity, bribery, money of the deceased, surgery, heavy debt beyond the power of the horoscope, low self-esteem and hard work, all at the same time. Many types of diseases, chronic diseases, diseases that cause great pain and suffering, illegal substances, excessive anger, loss of father at a young age, natural disasters, all kinds of unexpected good and bad events that a Jataka never dreamed of.

9th House Characters:

In physical aspect, the ninth Bhavakam representing the pelvic girdle, anus, etc. is trigona Bhavakam for Lagna Bhava, so it makes the karakas of Lagna Bhavaka flourish in a very noble position. Charakas that enhance the Jataka's personality, such as Godliness, Inference, Worship, Research, Honesty, Faith, Charity, High Thoughts, Humanity, Research, Intuition, Religious Belief, Acquiring Anything easily will differentiate one from others to a great extent. Our forefathers also called this as bagyasthan as the Ninth Bhavakam determines the fortune of the Jataka due to past deeds or the deeds of the Jataka in previous births. One of the main reasons is the system of giving a lot of respect to others due to one's actions, being very rich and donating a lot of wealth from others, lotteries, stock market, as fortunes such as the Ninth house of Bhavakam. Deep sleep, meditation, receiving instruction from Guru, meeting spiritualists, traditional thoughts, not leaving, deity works etc., the mind of the Jataka will go to non-economical things when the ninth house is running, and since the ninth house is trigon before lagna, it represents father in relationship and ancestors after father. . Generosity, Forethought, Long Distance Travel, Pilgrimage, Sea Travel, Air Travel, Abroad, Strangers, Higher Education, Universities, Nature Deities, Temple, Church, Mosque, Deity, Worshipful Persons, Guru, Foreign News, Long Distance News , radio, television, wireless telegraphy, spirit world communications, world experiences, law and order, judiciary, justice, legal arbitrator, export-import, international trade, inheritance, Freezing of money, loss of business, and the benefits and harms of past signs are the causes of the ninth house.

10th House Characters:

In the body element, the tenth Bhava represents the thighs, the organs that are always producing and functioning, such as the kidneys, liver, intestines, etc. A person's status, fame, recognition etc. are measured by the profession he does. 10th Bhavakam is the endowment of business when wealth is gained through economic activity. Self-earning of economy through business gives one status. A permanent job gives a person financial security. Kendras are stronger than each other just as triangles are stronger than each other, so the strongest of Kendras is the tenth house. 10th Bhavakam is an important Bhavakam in Bhava math calculation. This bhavakam is called the apex or peak of the horoscope. The 10th house indicates all the professions in the world, no matter what profession or job one is in, the 10th house plays an important role in achieving professional status, the tenth house must be strengthened in order for one to stay in the big positions in the business. Livelihood Earned by profession Social status, managerial ability, awareness and responsibility in anything, duty, authority, karmic rite for parents, unsatisfied attitude in

anything, reward from government, property of spouse, danger to younger brother, waste to elder brother, presiding over associational meetings, adopted child, Details of spouse's mother, mother-in-law, child's illness, always producing a product etc. are the factors of Tenth Bhavaka.

11th House Characters:

In anatomy eleventh house represents knees, joints and vitamins in the body, the eleventh house can tell if one is easily satisfied i.e. has the attitude of having enough. Success, net worth, profit, saving money without investing in anything, always being active and happy, discovering unknown secrets and gaining siddhi, being lively and happy with others, spending within the means and saving, progressing without obstacles in everything are the karakas of 11th house. The eleventh sign represents our long-term friends and well-wishers who are close to us. 11th Bhavakam is to collect a loan from someone in full. In Prasanna Astrology the eleventh sign plays an important role, especially whether one's desires are fulfilled or not. It can be known only through the 11th Bhavaka. The eleventh house refers to an elder brother or sister. It also indicates life partners of the horoscope's children i.e. son-in-law - daughter-in-law. Also one's desire, aspirations, goal, achievements, immunity in the body, vitamins, close friends of the horoscope, well-wishers of the horoscope, flatterers of the horoscope, saving habits, planning of efforts, satisfaction after fulfillment of desires, lasting friendship, group of like-minded people, Sangam meeting, conference, supreme education, full knowledge, thorough study in a field and getting doctor degree Ph.D., intelligence, parliament, legislature, municipalities, recovery from illness, return home from hospital etc.

12th House Characters:

In the body, the 12th bhava represents evils and waste products from the body. The 12th Bhavakam is the Bhavakam which ends all the functions of the Lagna horoscope. Our forefathers said that the 12th bhavakam is the place of moksha end because it shows the complete liberation of the horoscope from the cycle of birth and death and merges with the universe and nature. Ascendant means appearance and the 12th house can be said to be hidden or concealed, i.e. secret. So secret conspiracies, secret plans, conspiracies, secret enemies, murders for political reasons, unsolved riddles, hidden things, detective work, secret investments etc. are the causes of 12th house. 12th Bhavakam Dysfunction of body parts and brain Low attitude of the Jataka towards himself Being isolated without company of others Jataka not involved in anything, failure living in hiding, being kept away by social restrictions, prisons, orphanages, all kinds of hindrances, losses, excess expenses to the Jataka, excessive Repayment of loans with interest, inability to overcome hidden objections, secret imprisonment, hospital treatment, all kinds of punishments and fines, and renunciation of everything. At the same time 12th Bhavakam transfers, goes abroad, lives in a completely new situation, acquires citizenship abroad, invests money in property etc., gives one's job to someone else and is at ease, takes up a second career, establishes successive branches of business, finishes all work and goes to bed, Sleep also has the power to discover new things.

Types of Industries:

Industries are divided into two categories. One is intrinsically oriented industries and the second is extrinsically oriented industries. Here internal signs are 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11 which are internal signs. External signs are 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 which are external signs. The printing department is only good if it has these two signs i.e. internal and external, because if we have to express the thoughts that have appeared internally, if we want to write, it needs some tools like writing, and for that we have to take it from the external signs. All the tools and machinery used for printing are dependent on the outside. So if the printing industry wants to succeed, it needs machines. Iron, the raw material for machines, is an element dominated by Saturn. If we want to melt that iron, we can use the fiery planet Mars to melt that iron and make machines. Therefore Saturn, the ruler of iron and Mars, the cause of fire, can have both the planets, according to Kala Purusha philosophy, the tenth house sign is Makara Rasi. This Makara Rasi is ruled by Saturn, the Avita Nakshatra that can be in that sign, it is a star with Mars, so the tenth house is an external house, so it is only ten if the axis has internal signs, and only if there is a partner with external signs, this axis will be better. Objective in the study.

2nd bhavaka is speech, conversing, all actions done through our mouth are 2nd bhavaka. It is a peripheral behavior. If we leave the words, speech, and ideas that we have come up with as they are through this extraneous behavior, there is a chance that it will be destroyed in the course of time. That's why we have to embed these. The only equipment required for this is the mold. The 3rd Bhavakam is the Bhavakam corresponding to that axis. The 3rd Bhavaka is an evolutionary development of the 1st Bhavaka. That is, it is this 3rd Bhavaka that appears in the 1st Bhavakam and forms the thought, the letter. It was apparently created as a form of writing that could be used for all time, with the secondary use of external speech. It is timeless and created in a color that everyone can easily use. Therefore, this third house is also considered very important for the printing industry. Those who are good at the third house have more chances to excel in this printing industry. And through this we can know the necessity of Mercury in printing field. Man's nature, The bhavakam which can be called career is the 10th house. According to Kala purusha Tattva the third house is Gemini with Mercury as its lord, and the tenth house is Capricorn with Saturn as its lord. So we take these two planets and these two bhavas which are the house and planets required for printing industry. If we take the 3rd and 10th Bhavakas, the planets Mercury and Saturn and examine them, we are likely to get a lot more news.

The work of this first bhavaka only to make the thoughts. Second Bhavakam is Bhavakam which refers to speaking only. The third house is the only bhava which is used to write down one or two bhava. This third bhava has another characteristic and we can call this third bhava as evolution. And for each bhava, its third bhava is a bhava that represents evolution. When we see that, the first sign is the evolution of the thought through the third sign, the thought is evolved into letters. And if we take profession, it will always be the 10th Bhagavam. Because the tenth sign is a sign that one's Karuma can represent. Karuma is a verb that refers to one's work or profession. So what we need for this study is Third House, Gemini, Mercury. Aquarius, Saturn, and 10th house. Here we have to take Lagna as well because according to one's Lagna all the things that can happen in his life are included and we look at all things keeping the Lagna as the center so we need the Lagna for this study.

Therefore, when we think that a person should do well, in his horoscope, third house, Gemini, Mercury and Aquarius, Saturn should not be in 8th and 12th house for any reason. That means in your horoscope if Mercury and Saturn are in his Lagna 8, 12 Bhavas he will not be good in his printing business field.

- In this horoscope the lagna lord is Leo, its lord Sun is in Kendra, and it is in Scorpio.
- Third house is Libra sign; its lord Venus is getting kendra strength in Scorpio sign.
- 11th house is Gemini and its lord Mercury is in lagna kendra and 4th house is in Scorpio.
- Mercury is in Kendra Bhavakam in this horoscope.
- Saturn is in 11th Bhava.
- 10th Bhavagam Rishabha Rasi whose lord Venus gets Kendra strength and is in Scorpio.
- The fourth pada is the Ketta of nakshatra saram where the lord of the third bhava, Venus, is standing. It is the star of Mercury.
- Lagna lord Sun and Third lord Venus in this horoscope. 10th Lord Venus All three of them are in the star of Mercury in conjunction with Mercury.

Therefore, in this horoscope, the third house, eleventh house, lagna lord, Mercury, Saturn and tenth house are all very good. Based on that this Jataka is still doing his printing business for a long time.

Example Horoscope: 04
 Time of Birth: 01.40 PM

Date of Birth: 13.09.1988
 Place of Birth: Kovilpatti

Mar		Jup	
Rag	Rasi		Ven
			Keth Sun
Asc Sat			Moo Mer

Rag	Jup Sat		
	Navamsam		Moo
			Asc Mer
Sun	Mar	Ven	Keth

- In this example horoscope the third house is Aquarius, the lord of which is Saturn in the sign.
- The eleventh house lord Venus is in the eighth house to literature in Cancer.
- Mercury is in the 10th Bhavakam from the Ascendant in the sign of Virgo, ruling the Ascendant and Moolatrikona.
- 10th lord Mercury is in Virgo.
- Ascendant Sagittarius lord Guru is in 6th house in Taurus sign.
- Saturn is excellent in bhava of target.

This Jataka is facing a lot of obstacles to continue his printing business, because the Lagna lord Guru is in the 6th Bhavakam. Also Venus, the 11th lord of sign, is in the 8th house from the Ascendant. The 8th house lord Moon is co-joined with Mercury in the 10th house. Due to these reasons this horoscope is very difficult to do.

Example Horoscope: 05
 Time of Birth: 11.37 am

Date of Birth: 22.11.1973
 Place of Birth: Coimbatore

	Mar		Keth Sat
	Rasi		
Asc Jup			
Ven Rag	Sun	Mer Moo	

Mer	Mar	Jup Rag	
	Navamsam		Asc
Sat			Sun
Moo	Keth	Ven	

- The third house in this horoscope is Pisces and its lord is Guru Lagna Bhavagam is in triangle.
- Eleventh lord Mars, Aries Kendra gain strength is there.
- Mercury is in Libra in the 10th house.
- Saturn is in the 6th house from Lagna, Gemini.
- Venus, the lord of the 10th house, is in the 12th house to the lagna.
- The sign of this horoscope is in Capricorn. Its ruler is Saturn. Sixth house is in Gemini.

In this horoscope, the third house is the eleventh house. Planet Mercury. Saturn. These are very good. But even though the tenth house is in the 12th house for this horoscope, the karakas of other houses are good, so he has been doing printing business for the last 25 years.

Example Horoscope: 06
 Time of Birth: 01.55 PM

Date of Birth: 24.10.1972
 Place of Birth: Coimbatore

		Moo Sat	Keth
	Rasi		

			Keth Mer
	Navamsam		Jup Mar

Asc		Ven	
Jup Rag		Mer Sun	Mar

Moo			
Ven Sun Rag			Asc Sat

- In this example horoscope the Lagna lord is Capricorn, the lord Saturn is in trine aspect in Taurus, the Lagna lord is strong.
- Third house Pisces, its lord Guru is in twelfth house to lagna. And the essence of Ketu received by that Guru is in the house of Mercury in that Ketu Gemini.
- The eleventh house lord here is Scorpio, and that lord Mars is in the ninth house to the Ascendant in Virgo. It is in Trigona Bhava for Ascendant. So 11th lord is also good.
- In this horoscope, Mercury is gaining Kendra strength in the 10th house.
- Saturn is gaining trine strength in fifth house in this horoscope.
- The tenth lord is also the evil lord in this horoscope. Eighth lord of sign. Because they are interchanging. Tenth house can be considered as strong.
- Also Lagna lord Saturn is in Virgo Navamsa. This is also an added strength for a lagna lord.

So third place in this horoscope. 11th place. Planet Mercury. He has been doing very well in the printing industry for the last 20 years due to Saturn, Lagna lord and 10th lord being all good.

Example Horoscope: 07
 Time of Birth: 08.33 PM

Date of Birth: 05.03.1969
 Place of Birth: Ooty

Sat Rag	Ven		
Sun	Rasi		
Mer			
	Mar		Asc Keth Mo Jup

Sat Ket Jup Mo	Sun Ven		
	Navamsam		Asc
		Mar	Mer Rag

- In this horoscope the third house Scorpio is in the same house as its lord Mars, so the third house is good.
- Eleventh house Cancer is in Virgo with its lord Moon in Lagna. It is a Mercury house. So the eleventh house is also good.
- 10th Bhavagam Gemini with its lord Mercury in Ascendant in trigonal bava, fifth sign Capricorn is a specialty.
- Virgo Lagna is in Capricorn, the fifth house from its lord Mercury Lagna.
- Both Mercury and Saturn are in kendra and trigona bhavas in this horoscope i.e. Mercury is in trigon and Saturn is in kendra house.
- Third house lord Mars is the essence of Anusham Third pada This is the essence of Saturn.
- Also Lagna lord Mercury is in Virgo in Navamsa which still adds strength to Lagna and 10th Bhavaka.

So in this horoscope there are third house, eleventh house, lagna house and tenth house. He has been doing printing as his sole profession for the last 30 years due to the fact that Mercury and Saturn are all good.

Example Horoscope: 08
 Time of Birth: 12.15 PM

Date of Birth: 20.01.1973
 Place of Birth: Coimbatore

	Asc	Sat	Keth
	Rasi		Mo
Sun Mer			
Jup Rag Ven	Mar		

Sun		Ket	Asc
Mo	Navamsam		Sat
Mar Mer			
Jup	Rag		Ven

- The third house in this horoscope is Gemini, its lord Mercury is in the tenth house from the Ascendant.
- 11th house Aquarius is in second house to its lord Saturn Lagna.
- In this horoscope, Lagna lord Mars is ruling Scorpio in his house.
- 10th lord Saturn is in 2nd house to lagna.
- In this horoscope, Mercury is gaining strength in the 10th house.
- Saturn is in second house in this horoscope.

Therefore, he has been doing his printing business for the last 30 years, third house, the eleventh house, the Lagna house, and the tenth house are Wednesday and Saturn are all strong.

Example Horoscope: 09
 Time of Birth: 10.15 AM

Date of Birth: 04.12.1981
 Place of Birth: Coimbatore

			Rag
Mo	Rasi		
Asc Ven			
Keth	Mer Sun	Jup	Sat Mar

	Asc		Rag
	Navamsam		
Mo Ven Mar			Sat
Sun Jup Ket	Mer		

- In this horoscope the third house Pisces is in the tenth house to its lord Guru lagna.
- Mars, the 11th lord of this horoscope, is in the ninth house to Lagna in Virgo.
- Lagna Capricorn is in Virgo in ninth house to its lord Saturn Lagna.
- The 10th house Libra sign has its lord Venus in Lagna.
- In this horoscope Mercury is in the eleventh house from Lagna.
- In this horoscope Saturn is in the ninth house from Lagna.

So in this horoscope Lagna lord is tenth lord, third lord and eleventh lord. Mercury and Saturn are excellent for all these. His printing business has been going on for the past 15 years.

Example Horoscope: 10
 Time of Birth: 02.30 PM

Date of Birth: 21.03.1973
 Place of Birth: Madurai

Sun Ven		Sat	Keth
Mer	Rasi		Asc
Mar Jup			
Rag		Mo	

Ket	Jup	Mer	
	Navamsam		Sat Ven
Mar			
	Mo		Asc Sun Rag

- The third house in this horoscope is Virgo. Its lord Mercury is in eighth house to Lagna in Aquarius.
- Taurus is the 11th sign for Ascendant in this horoscope. Its lord Venus is having supreme strength in the ninth house to the Ascendant.
- Cancer Ascendant has Kendra strength in 4th Bhavakam to its lord Moon Ascendant.
- The 10th house is Aries and its lord Mars is placed in Capricorn in the seventh house to the Lagna.
- In this horoscope Mercury is placed in Aquarius in eighth house.
- In this horoscope Saturn is in the 11th house to Lagna.

So this Jataka could not do well in his printing business, because the third house lord Mercury is in the eighth house to Ascendant, this Jataka could not do well in his business.

Example Horoscope: 11
 Time of Birth: 12.16 PM

Date of Birth: 19.03.1995
 Place of Birth: Tiruchirappalli

Sun	Keth		Asc
Mer Sat	Rasi		Mar
Ven			
	Jup	Mo Rag	

	Sat		
	Navamsam		Ket
Rag Mer Jup			Sun Ven
Asc Mar	Mo		

- The third house in this horoscope is Leo. Its lord Sun is in the 10th house from the Ascendant in Pisces.
- 11th house is Aries and its lord Mars is in Cancer sign in second house to lagna.
- Here Lagna is Gemini, its lord Mercury is in ninth house to Lagna in Aquarius.
- The 10th house is Pisces and its lord Guru is in the 6th house to the Ascendant.
- In this horoscope, Mercury and Saturn are trigonal to the ascendant in the ninth house.

So he has been working in a Printing Press for the past five years.

Example Horoscope: 12
 Time of Birth: 01.30 PM

Date of Birth: 25.03.1981
 Place of Birth: Coimbatore

Mar Sun Ven			Asc		Jup Sat	Ket	Asc
Mer	Rasi		Rag	Mer	Navamsam		Mo
Keth							
	Mo		Jup Sat		Rag	Sun Mar	Ven

- Sun (Leo) is the third house lord in this horoscope. That Sun is in the 10th house from Lagna.
- The 11th house lord Mars (Aries) is in the 10th house.
- Gemini Ascendant, The ascendant lord Mercury is in the ninth house to the Ascendant. (Aquarius).
- 10th Bhavakam Here Pisces sign is in Virgo with its lord Guru in fourth bhavakam.
- Mercury is in ninth house in this horoscope.
- In this horoscope Saturn is in the 4th house to Lagna.

So this Jataka is running his father's printing business.

Conclusion:

At the end of this study we have taken rules like third house, 11th house, lagna, tenth house. We have been able to examine how Mercury and Saturn fit well in the printer's castes. And in this study we were able to study how the print industry is related to astrology, how much influence of Mercury and how much influence of Saturn in the print industry. Through this study we have come to know that if there are only planets then all ten Bhavakas are required.

How the three and eleven Bhavakas support the axis sector, according to Kala Purusha theory, the third Bhavaka is also Gemini which is an air sign, the eleventh Bhavaka is Aquarius which is also an air sign, the lord of Gemini is Mercury. Lord of Aquarius is Saturn. The word we speak goes through the air to the ear of the person in front of us and that is how this printing industry must have appeared. So, my study reveals that the causes of this third cycle, such as cell phones, radio sets, televisions, and telegraphs, are all based on air.

All the thoughts that arise in the First Bhavaka are perfected in the Third Bhavaka, which is the evolution of the First Bhavaka. That is, thoughts arise in our first bhava and they evolve into letters in the third bhava. So the third virtue is the quality of life of a human being. Through this study we can know that it is a very important practice to improve the society.

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